

Determinants of Information Communication Technology Adoption on Supply Chain Performance in Manufacturing Sector in Kenya

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Abstract:

The main aim of the paper was to assess the determinants of ICT adoption on supply chain performance with Bamburi Cement Kenya Limited as the case study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Due to the homogeneity of the target population, a simple random sampling technique was used to select 80 respondents. Questionnaires were the major instrument for data collection. Data collected was analyzed by use of the SPSS software Version 23 for both descriptive and inferential statistics. The results from the analysis indicated that top management support and buyer/supplier integration have a positive and significant effect on supply chain performance. It is recommended for the top management to have a high level of commitment to the use of ICT in the supply chain. Also, it is important for manufacturing firms to make use of IT to send tender specifications to suppliers and ensure that there is an electronic interaction with international and local new suppliers. Finally, there is a need for manufacturing firms to capitalize on ICT as it has the potential to reduce the cost incurred while sending information and during transportation

Keywords: Top Management Support, Buyer/Supplier Integration, Commitment, Supply Chain Performance

Introduction

The adoption and usage of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is changing business processes and the way people live and work. New innovations as a result of ICT are continuing to emerge. ICT means information and communications technologies including cell phone and Internet services, radio, and a wide range of digital devices and related tools including cameras, GIS, and a wide range of hand-held computing devices. ICT enhances the integration and expansion of value chains and workflows beyond organizational boundaries (Kamotho, 2014). ICT is significantly valued in its capacity to bring up linkages and collaborations among the business world. ICT adoption (hardware and software), has provided solutions to most organizations of the world by way of economically utilizing time and money to its maximum productivity by making the following interventions in their supply chain, reducing costs of coordination (collection of production and distribution of inputs), increasing transparency in decision making between partners, reducing transaction cost, disseminating market demand and price information, disseminating weather, pest, and risk-management information disseminating best practices to meet quality and certification standards, collecting management data from the field and ensuring traceability (Kotla, 2011).

In supply chain management, ICT has especially been recognized as an enabler for information sharing which companies in the supply chain can use for eliminating the so called bullwhip-effect (Lee et al., 1997). Information-sharing is also a key component in many of the recent automatic replenishment programs (ARP) (Daugherty et al., 1999). Initiatives such as vendor managed inventory (VMI) and collaborative planning, forecasting and replenishment (CPFR) is based on an increased level of automation in both the flow of physical materials and goods and the flow of information between companies to improve the efficiency in the entire supply chain. In a operations management perspective, companies seek to further improve the efficiency in the supply chain by sharing information related to matching demand and supply such as short- and long-term production planning, demand forecasting and materials, and capacity planning. Information that can be relevant to share between customers and suppliers typically includes point-of-sales data, forecasts and inventory levels. There is a significant amount of research demonstrating a positive impact of ICT in the supply chain. As companies seek to improve the efficiency in the supply chain through increased integration, ICT can be considered as a key enabler for supply chain management through its ability to support information sharing and

shortening information processing time. Supply chain integration can, however, be expressed in a wide range of dimensions such as integration of processes, information, organisations, and systems (Bowersox et al., 1999; Mouritsen et al., 2003).

In offering chain management, ICT has particularly been recognised as AN enabler for info sharing that corporations within the offer chain will use for eliminating the thus referred to as bullwhip-effect (Lee et al., 2017). Information-sharing is additionally a key element in several of the recent automatic replacement programs (ARP) (Daugherty et al., 2009). Initiatives like merchandiser managed inventory (VMI) and collaborative coming up with, statement ANd replacement (CPFR) are supported an accrued level of automation in each the flow of physical materials and merchandise and also the flow of data between companies to boost the potency within the entire offer chain. in a very operations management perspective, companies get to additional improve the potency within the offer chain by sharing info associated with matching demand and provide like short- and long production coming up with, demand statement and materials and capability coming up with info that may be relevant to share between customers and suppliers usually includes point-of-sales knowledge, forecasts and inventory levels. There is a large quantity of analysis demonstrating a positive impact of ICT within the offer chain. As companies get to boost the potency within the offer chain through accrued integration, ICT can be considered as a key enabler for offer chain management through its ability to support information sharing and shortening scientific discipline time offer chain integration will but be expressed in a wide selection of dimensions like integration of processes, information, organizations and systems (Mouritsen, et al., 2013).

According to Mwilu (2013), in the financial year 2010/2011 alone, the manufacturing sector in Kenya accounts for 16.3% of the Nations nominal GDP an estimated \$29.964 billion, making the manufacturing sector third in the overall stake after agriculture and service firms. This makes the manufacturing sector a key industry in the Kenyan economy. The economic contribution of this sector is immense, with significance linkages to the manufacturing and services sectors (Dehning et al., 2007). Given the significant challenges facing the industry, in particular globalization, liberalization and increasing competition, a considerable amount of pressure on Kenyan manufacturers to shorten time to market, increase customer service levels, provide higher level of conformance and quality, and offer more variety in product lines has resulted (Biggs et al., 2002). Manufacturers today have been forced to increase their resilience to remain competitive domestically and identify the new potential for exploiting the local, as well as the global market. In order to achieve these aims, coping with supply chain technology (SCT) appears to be a necessity (Jin, 2006). Onyango (2011) studied supply chain management practices and performance in the cement industry in Kenya. Elias et al., (2012) observed that the adoption of some supply chain management technologies in the manufacturing sector in Kenya would bring about competitiveness within the manufacturing sector both locally and internationally. On the same note, Chepkoech & Noor (2014) investigated the effects of Enterprise resource planning implementation on supply chain performance in the manufacturing sector in Kenya. On the other hand, Nkatha (2014) investigated Information and Communication Technology Adoption and Supply Chain Performance among Cooperative Societies in Embu County in Kenya. Further, Samir K. Srivastava (2007) undertook a study on the importance of ICT on green supply chain management in the manufacturing sector. E.W.T Ngai (2003) studied Information systems in supply chain integration and management. No clear studies have therefore been done on the important topic on the determinants of adoption of ICT on supply chain performance in the manufacturing sector. To this regard, this study undertakes to investigate the determinants of ICT adoption on supply chain performance in the manufacturing sector in Kenya with a focus on Bamburi Cement Co. Limited. The study was guided by the following objectives;

- *To establish if top management support affects supply chain performance in Bamburi Cement Limited.*
- *To find out if buyer/supplier intergration affects supply chain performance in Bamburi Cement Limited.*

Theoretical Framework

The theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 2011) is an extension of the theory of reasoned action (TRA). Ajzen (1991), made necessary by the latter model's inability to deal with behaviors over which individuals have incomplete volitional control unless supported by top level management. At the heart of TPB is the organization's top management support to perform a given behavior (e.g., use of ICT applications in the supply chain). For TPB, attitude toward the target behavior and subjective norms about engaging in the behavior are thought to influence intention, and TPB includes perceived behavioral control over engaging in the behavior as a factor influencing intention. Kandelousi et al. (2011) mentioned that top management support could be viewed in several forms, for example, helping teams in dealing with hurdles, exhibiting a commitment to the work and encouraging the subordinates. Usually top management support results in the availability of in time financial resources, allocation of human and other physical resources and also it refers to the delegation of necessary power to project leaders and project team for successful completion of projects. Moreover, top management support is an important recommendation in the achievement of project success (Belassi and Tukel, 1996; Chae and Poole, 2005; Lin, 2010). researchers suggested that for successful implementation of ICT projects, top management should represent themselves as project champions (McComb et al., 2008; Naranjo-Gil, 2009). Project championing is referred to communicating the vital importance of the project very clearly, in addition, resolving conflicts and supporting the project team (Beath, 1991; Morton, 1983)

Literature Review

Top Management Support

Top management support is recommended to be examined as one of the value drivers that trigger reverse logistics performance within an organization. It ensured the success of the reverse logistics process by emphasizing on the areas of organizational buy-in, continuous improvement, the definition of mission for the system, and clear purpose (Huscroft, 2008). Relatively less importance given to the reverse logistics by the top management has been taken as one of the managerial inefficiency for considering the success factors of the reverse logistics process (Verweij et al. 2008). According to the resource based view of the organizations, deploying the organizational resources in the most effective and efficient opportunities available, organizations can enjoy a defensibly long competitive edge. There is just a need to create a correct match between organizational resources and available opportunities. Top management's resource commitment in different support programs like information support program is essential for the overall success of reverse logistics.

Daugherty, Richey, Genchev & Chen, (2005) empirically proved the high performance of reverse logistics by inducting proper resources in the technology improvement programs. The study evidenced that it will ultimately enhance the information support capability of the organizations. Daugherty et al. (2005) compared the high performing and average performing firms in the context of technological resource commitment. The tested the impact of top management resource commitment and information support system on organizational, economic performance and quality of the services being rendered. Findings and results suggested that the positive relation between resource commitment and the two constructs of financial performance and service quality is not significant.

But they have also mentioned that it does not mean that resource commitment is not important. It has a certain impact on organizational reverse logistics programs (Daugherty et al. 2005). As reported by another study that for the successful Supply chain performance of reverse logistics, there is a need to create a sense of strategic focus in the reverse logistics program (Smith, 2005). Top management triggers the reverse logistics strategy in order to gain a competitive advantage for the organization.

Buyer-supplier integration

Humphreys (2001) described Information technology (IT) as the application of computers and telecommunications equipment to store, retrieve, transmit and manipulate data, often in the context of a business or other enterprise. A study carried out by Li (2003) found out that telecommunications and computer technology allow all the actors in the supply chain to communicate with each other. Lyons (2006) stated that information technology (IT) had become a vital and integral part of every business plan.

In effect to SRM principles, Handfield (1999) indicated that the use of information technology allows suppliers, organizations, distributors, retailers, and customers to reduce lead time, paperwork, and other unnecessary activities. It is also mentioned that managers will experience considerable advantages with its use such as the flow of information in a coordinated manner, access to information and data interchange, improved customer and supplier relationships, and inventory management not only at the national level but also internationally. Also, the advantages will include supply contracts via the internet, distribution of strategies, outsourcing, and procurement. All companies are looking for cost and lead time reductions with the purpose of improving the level of service but also to enhance inter-organizational relationships (Humphreys, 2001).

Lyons (2006) indicates that firms cannot effectively manage cost, offer high customer service, and become leaders in supply chain management without the incorporation of top-of-the-line information technologies. Larson (2000) identified 14 such information technology tools, among them electronic data interchange (EDI), enterprise resource planning (ERP), internet, and extranets. Li grouped these tools into three groups in terms of their primary purpose: communication tools, resource planning tools, and supply chain management tools.

Research Gap

From the empirical review, of the study it is a clear indication that varied scholars and researchers of the world have made numerous attempts to explain various issues surrounding supply chain performance. These scholars have also discussed the aspects of ICT adoption. However, no major study or a theoretical explanation has successfully managed to elaborate on the key determinants of ICT adoption specifically on supply chain performance in the manufacturing sector in Kenya. This has hence influenced the development of major knowledge gaps on the aspect of ICT adoption in the larger supply chain in manufacturing organizations, hence necessitating the need to conduct a study to critically observe and evaluate the determinants of ICT adoption on supply chain performance in the manufacturing sector in Kenya. In this regard, the research seeks to narrow down to aspects; organization policy, top management support, buyer/supplier integration and cost reduction to help develop an adequate conclusion and recommendations in the Kenyan manufacturing sector.

Methodology

A descriptive survey involves an attempt to collect data from members of a certain population with the aim of determining the current status of that population with respect to one or more variables. For purposes of this study, the target population constituted employees in the top management level, middle level managers and support staff in the procurement, marketing, HRM, Accounting and finance departments. In total, 400 employees across departments in Bamburi Cement Limited constituted the target population. The sample of 80 was obtained using Nassiuma's (2000) sample size formula. Semi-structured questionnaires were the major method for data collection. A pilot study was carried out to determine the reliability of the questionnaires. Reliability analysis was subsequently done using Cronbach's Alpha which measures the internal consistency by establishing if certain items within a scale measure the same construct. Table 4.2 below shows that top management support had the highest reliability ($\alpha=0.945$), followed by supply chain performance ($\alpha=0.911$), then buyer/supplier integration ($\alpha=0.821$). This illustrates that all the five scales were reliable as their reliability

values exceeded the prescribed threshold of 0.7. This, therefore, depicts that the research instrument was reliable and therefore required no amendments. Descriptive statistics, in this case, were employed to analyze the data collected by the researcher where statistical measures of central tendency-mean and standard deviation were utilized to analyze responses under specific variables. SPSS software Version 23 were the main tools for data analysis.

Findings

This section presents and discusses the results of this study based on the formulated objectives and research questions as presented in chapter one. the researcher distributed 80 questionnaires to the respondents.79 questionnaires out of the 80 were returned, which gives a response rate of approximately 98.75%. This response rate is above average. Even though the percentage rate of response was above average, the number of distributed questionnaires may have implications on the validity of the statistical analysis. The writer did, however, decide to continue with the analysis because the theoretical part of the project was already done.

Sample characteristics

The demographic characteristics sought from the respondents included; age, gender, education level and experience in the supply chain. The demographic information or characteristics concerning the unit under investigation gives the researcher a glimpse into other factors other than the main factors which are or might be acting as confounders in a given phenomenon and which might determine the direction of the relationship between the main factors under investigation. The findings show that 45 (57%) of the employees are male while 34 (43%) are female. Although there is a clear bias toward males, the proportion of females is more than a third of the employees. The findings also show that 53 (67.1%) of the employees are below 30 years of age indicating a youthful workforce, 23 (29.1%) are between 31 and 40 years of age while 3 (3.8%) are between 41 and 50 years of age. Cumulatively, over 96% of the workforce in Bamburi Cement is below 40 years of age. Regarding education, the findings show that only 3 (3.8%) of the employees are Ph.D. degree holders, 13 (16.5%) have master's education, 34 (43%) have bachelor's education while 29 (36.7%) are diploma holders. These findings show that the firm has employed staff with diverse education and professional qualification levels and chances of conflict due to misinterpretation of information and of directives were unavoidable. In addition, these diversities provide a means of obtaining a diverse set of information regarding the subject matter. Finally, the findings show that 19 (24.1%) of the employees have been working in supply chain for less than 3 years, 29 (36.7%) have an experience of between 4 to 6 years, 23 (29.1%) have an experience of between 7 to 9 years while only 8 (10.1%) have worked for 10 years or more. Cumulatively, over 89% of the employees have worked for less than 9 years which is comparable with the age of majority of the employees, aged below 40 years. On the other hand, there is diversity in terms of employment; hence the expectation is that there are different levels of understanding of the subject matter.

Descriptive and Correlation Analysis

Kandelousi, Ooi & Abdollahi (2011) mentions that top management support can be viewed in several forms, for example, helping teams in dealing with hurdles, exhibiting a commitment to the work and encouraging the subordinates. Thus, using a 5- point Likert scale, the study sought to establish the perspectives of the employees of Bamburi Cement regarding top management supports and the findings were presented in Table 1. The overall mean was 3.56 (SD = 0.780) regarding top management support. Buyer/supplier commitment is the belief that trading partners are willing to devote energy to sustaining the relationship. Thus, the study sought to determine the perspectives of the employees regarding the level of collaboration between the buyer and supplier and eventually how this might influence supply chain performance in Bamburi Cement. Generally, the mean response was 3.65 (SD = 0.637) for buyer/supplier integration indicating that there was a considerable level of

IT integration in the supply chain processes. This level of integration is only on the posting of tender documents that enables potential suppliers to download them. However, the level of IT integration is sub-optimal especially in sending of tender specifications and tender prices to suppliers and tender responses from suppliers, interaction with international and local new suppliers with the least in terms of IT integration being an evaluation of new supplier capabilities. Based on these findings, especially in relation to the gaps identified in terms of the level of IT integration, Handfield (1999) indicated that the use of information technology allows suppliers, organizations, distributors, retailers, and customers to reduce lead time, paperwork, and other unnecessary activities. Lyons (2006) indicates that firms cannot effectively manage cost, offer high customer service, and become leaders in supply chain management without the incorporation of top of-the-line information technologies. Supply Chain Management as the process of planning, implementing and controlling efficient and cost effective flow of materials, in-process inventory, finished goods and related information from point-of-order to point-of-consumption, for the purpose of conforming to customer requirements. The fundamental objective of the high performance of the supply chain is to produce products to match customers demand cycle while producing the greatest value possible to the customers. The increasingly competitive environment calls for speedy, cost efficient, accurate and reliable supply chain. Thus, the study sought to establish the views of the employees in the manufacturing sector in Kenya regarding the level of supply chain performance especially given the perceived level of organizational policy, top management support, buyer/supplier integration, and cost reduction. Their views were measured using a 5- point Likert scale to indicate their degree of agreement or disagreement with various aspects that define supply chain performance, and the findings were presented in Table 4.8. Generally, the mean response regarding supply chain performance was 4.02 (SD = 0.780) indicating a considerable level of supply chain performance in the manufacturing sector in Kenya. Despite suppliers delivering the correct quantity of goods, willingness to adjust products/services to meet changing needs and short order to delivery cycle time, there are gaps identified in terms of quality and service levels, delivery time, prices/ cost and flexibility of the suppliers. Based on these findings, the gaps identified might be sourced from such facts as sub-optimal levels of integration of essential factors such as IT in the supply chain process. Emiliani (2003) indicated that service companies should improve their SCM performance through a number of critical measures of performance that need to be continuously monitored through (KPI). The three key outcomes of success are better, faster, cheaper.

Furthermore, although correlations are important, they do not infer cause and effect relationship. Thus, the study sought to establish the nature of the relationships existing between the independent variables and the dependent variable by examining the correlation coefficients. Consequently, a correlation analysis of the independent factors and the dependent factor (supply chain performance) was conducted and the findings were summarized and presented in Table 1. The findings in Table 1 show that top management support has a positive and significant relationship with supply chain performance, $\rho = 0.621$, $p < 0.001$. In addition, buyer/supplier integration has a positive and significant relationship with supply chain performance, $\rho = 0.771$, $p < 0.001$. There are also significant inter-factor relationships that point to the fact that they are mutually dependent. These findings show that the various supply chain elements complement each other for the benefit of increasing the level of supply chain performance in the manufacturing sector in Kenya.

Table 1: Descriptive and Correlation Results

	Supply Chain Performance	Top management support	Buyer/supplier integration
Supply Chain Performance	4.02	0.78	1
Top management support	3.56	0.78	.621**
Buyer/supplier integration	3.65	0.637	.771**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression model

The regression analysis, in this case, is used to assess the effect of the independent factors on the dependent factor (supply chain performance) and answer the underlying research questions. First, the model summary and the analysis of variance which is used in assessing model fit were assessed, and findings were presented in Table 2. The regression analysis findings are used in answering the research questions for the study. The findings in Table 2 on the model summary show that all the predictors explain 68.2% of the variation in supply chain performance ($R = 0.826$, R -squared = 0.682, Adjusted R -squared = 0.664). The coefficient of determination explains the extent to which changes in the response variable can be explained by the change in the explanatory variables or the percentage of variation in the dependent variable that is explained by all the independent variable. ANOVA results in Table 2 show that the model fit was good as illustrated by the overall test of significance with $F(4, 74)$ value of 39.607 with $p < 0.001$. Thus, the model was fit to predict supply chain performance based on various supply relationship management factors.

Effect of top management support on supply chain performance

The second objective of this study was to find out if top management support affects supply chain performance at Bamburi Cement Limited. The study aimed to answer the research question that: Does top management support with affect supply chain performance at Bamburi Cement Limited? The findings in Table 4.12 show that top management support has a positive and significant effect on supply chain performance, $\beta_2 = 0.206$, $p = 0.017$. This means that with each unit increase in top management support, supply chain performance increases by 0.206 units. In line with these findings,

Effect of buyer/supplier intergration on supply chain performance

The third specific objective of this study was to ascertain whether buyer/supplier intergration affect supply chain performance at Bamburi Cement Limited. In line with this objective, the study sought to answer the research question: How does buyer/supplier intergration affect supply chain performance at Bamburi Cement Limited? From the findings in Table 4.12, buyer/supplier intergration has a positive and significant effect on supply chain performance, $\beta_3 = 0.379$, $p = 0.002$. This means that with each unit increase in buyer/supplier intergration, supply chain performance would increase by 0.379 units. These findings support those of Togar (2002) who states that optimum collaboration is achieved when collective intelligence is at its best - in other words, it goes beyond the sum of individual contributions. This can be achieved when you allow instant collaboration anywhere and at any time with both internal and external personnel, and when all of the information that is required is available and is used. Spekman (2006) established that a successful buyer-supplier collaborative relationship is often characterized by a high level of trust, commitment, shared values, communication, adaptation, positive bases of power, cooperation, and relationship bonds.

Table 1: Multiple Regression Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.639	0.263		2.43	0.018
Top management support	0.191	0.078	0.206	2.436	0.017
Buyer/supplier intergration	0.351	0.107	0.379	3.274	0.002
Model summary results					
<i>R Square</i>	0.682				
<i>Adjusted R Square</i>	0.664				
<i>F</i>	39.607				
<i>Sig.</i>	0.000b				

Conclusion and Recommendations

Furthermore, top management support has an enhancing effect on supply chain performance, and this is mainly due to the fact that the top management ensures there are adequate resources for the implementation of ICT. Concisely, through top management support, there is long-term training for the use of ICT. Other than that, it ensures that there is good communication between the top management and use of ICT thereby enhancing a clear understanding of ICT use in the supply chain.

The findings have also shown that enhancement of buyer/supplier integration has an incremental effect on supply chain performance. However, there are gaps in terms of whether the firm utilizes IT to send tender specifications to suppliers and if the firm receives a tender response from suppliers electronically. There are also gaps in terms of communication since there is limited evidence of electronic communication of tender prices. The only hope with buyer/supplier integration is that the firm electronically posts tender documents which can be downloaded easily.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed: The top management support is vital in the supply chain process. In fact, the support of the top management results in improved supply chain performance. There is, therefore, need for the top management to have a high level of commitment in the use of ICT in the supply chain. Also, there is a need for the top management to maintain long-term training for the use of ICT. Moreover, it is important for the management to be highly responsive to the use of ICT. In so doing, the supply chain performance will be improved.

Since buyer/supplier integration has a positive and significant effect on supply chain performance, there is a need for manufacturing firms to post tender documents electronically. This will enhance efficiency in the supply chain and make it easier for suppliers to download the tender documents easily. Moreover, it is utmost necessary for manufacturing firms to make use of IT to send tender specifications to suppliers and ensure that there is an electronic interaction with international and local new suppliers.

This study focuses on Bamburi Cement limited in Kenya only. However, there is a need to increase the scope to cover other manufacturing firms in Kenya so as to confirm the findings of this study and also to add more knowledge. Furthermore, while there are firm-specific factors that determine the direction of supplier relationship management and how this influences supply chain performance; there are factors that are inherent from the external environment in terms of policies and operational procedures that might have an influence on supply chain performance. Thus, there is need to have a deeper look into the determinants of the external environment more, in terms of practices and policies, so as to get an overview of the challenges with a view of addressing them from all angles.

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